

Rationalisation of the Tsai-Wu Failure Criterion

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to rationalise the empirical aspect of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion associated with the determination of the interactive strength property F_{12} based on the analytical geometry according to which the condition of closed failure envelope cannot be satisfied by all unidirectionally fibre reinforced composites (UD) and hence should be abandoned. Depending on the way the failure envelope opens, UD composites can be classified into two categories. (a) F_{12} can be determined uniquely using the conventional strength properties with an additional assumption that the material exhibit very high or infinite strength under triaxial compression at a specific stress ratio; or (b) The Tsai-Wu criterion lead to one of the two scenarios: either allowing infinite strength for an in-plane stress state or to allow infinite strength under infinite number of triaxial stress ratios, some involving tension along fibres. The rationalisation supplements the existing understanding with generic facts which have hitherto not been revealed. The validity of the new assumption can only be proven by experiments which are scarce. A call for relevant experimental data is generated through this paper in order to assess the likelihood of very high or infinite strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

The state-of-the-art of composite failure criteria has been documented as the outcomes of World Wide Failure Exercises (WWFEs) [1-3]. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion is one of the earliest failure criteria proposed for UD composites in a comprehensive and non-phenomenological manner [4]. Over the past decades, the criterion has enjoyed remarkable success as it has been employed by researchers and designers all over the world. It has been included in most textbooks on the subject of composites, e.g. [5]. It has also been incorporated in commercial FE codes, e.g. [6]. On the other hand, it has been subjected to criticism for being non-phenomenological without due consideration of the failure mechanisms by employing a single quadratic function to account for all possible failure modes observed in experiments [7]. More recent attempts of appraising it can be found in [8,9]. Tsai and his co-worker have continued to work to enable more convenient applications [10,11].

There has been one issue of the Tsai-Wu criterion which has never been thoroughly investigated, i.e. the empiricism associated with one of the interactive coefficients F_{12} . Given the nature of the failure criterion, determination of it through experimental means proves to be difficult as applying biaxial loads up to the failure of the material at a representative stress ratio has always been a challenge. The way F_{12} was obtained in the Tsai-Wu criterion is empirical supported by limited test results. Although the Tsai-Wu failure criterion has been a well-known theory in the composites community, favoured by some while objected by others, these judgements might have been made without the full facts. The objective of this paper is offer one final fact associated with the determination of the interactive coefficient, F_{12} , on a rational basis to eliminate the empiricism.

2 THE ORIGINAL TSAI-WU CRITERION

In addition to conventional assumptions, such as homogeneity and linear elasticity up to failure, the original Tsai-Wu criterion [4] was based three major assumptions:

- i) The failure is determined by a single quadratic function of stresses;
- ii) The material is transversely isotropic; and
- iii) The failure envelope is closed.

After giving due considerations to the material symmetry, the quadratic function

$$F = F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}(\sigma_2^2 + \sigma_3^2) + (2F_{22} - F_{44})\sigma_2\sigma_3 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1(\sigma_3 + \sigma_2) + F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_3\sigma_3 + F_{44}\tau_{23}^2 + F_{66}\tau_{13}^2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 \quad (1)$$

for a general 3D stress state was given as the failure function with the critical condition for failure predicted when

$$F = 1. \quad (2)$$

Most of the coefficients involved in (1) can be determined from the conventional strength of UD composites as follows

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{1t}^*\sigma_{1c}^*}, \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}, \quad F_1 = \frac{1}{\sigma_{1t}^*} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{1c}^*}, \quad F_2 = \frac{1}{\sigma_{2t}^*} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{2c}^*}$$

$$F_{44} = \frac{1}{(\tau_{23}^*)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{(\tau_{12}^*)^2} \quad (3)$$

with σ_{1t}^* and σ_{1c}^* being the tensile and compressive strengths of the material along fibres, σ_{2t}^* and σ_{2c}^* those in the direction transverse to the fibres, and τ_{12}^* and τ_{23}^* the shear strengths along and transverse to fibres. These conventional strength properties of typical UD composites should be obtained when they are loaded under uniaxial stress states or pure shear stress states in their material's principal axis. There are standards available for the experimental measurement of them, e.g. [12,13].

There is still one coefficient F_{12} which has not yet been specified above and it should ideally be determined through biaxial stress tests. Given the difficulties in conducting this type of tests and the lack of standard testing procedure, no standard experimental method is available to determine it.

In their original paper, Tsai and Wu [4] insisted that the failure envelope must be an ellipsoid and hence remains closed. According to analytical geometry [14], this condition offers some constraints on F_{12} but the constraints are given as ranges rather than any fixed value for F_{12} .

For most applications under in-plane stresses, (1) can be rewritten in its 2D form as

$$F = F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2. \quad (4)$$

As F_{12} involves only direct stresses σ_1 and σ_2 , some considerations will be made later when the material is subject to biaxial direct stresses, where condition (2) is simplified to

$$F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 = 1. \quad (5)$$

This defines a typical conic section in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ plane. The condition for the failure locus on the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ plane to be an ellipse is given largely as

$$F_{12}^2 < F_{11}F_{22}. \quad (6)$$

However, this only defines a range for F_{12} , which appears to be rather wide in most cases. The complete determination of F_{12} remains as an issue to be resolved. It has been left as an empirical parameter [15]. One form of it has been suggested as [16]

$$F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} \quad (7)$$

which was expressed in terms of conventional strength properties. The justifications for this particular form are

- (a) It falls in the range as defined by (6), and
- (b) It allows itself to be degenerated to that of von Mises if the material is specialised to isotropic having equal tensile and compressive strengths.

While some may argue that it fits well with some of the experiments, others can always produce a counterargument in other cases. Expression (7) is by no means the only form having the feature as stated in (b) above, as will be seen later in this paper, nor a fully rational one, either. The focus of the present paper is on this coefficient where hitherto empiricism has been the norm [17]. Extra rational considerations will be introduced leading to the unique determination of this coefficient for a wide range of UD composites. As will be seen later, there are exceptions which will have to be dealt with differently as will be shown.

3 ABANDONMENT OF CLOSED FAILURE ENVELOPE RESTRICTION

The possibility of an open failure envelope was categorically rejected in [4]. However, it is revealing to examine the failure locus on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane where $\sigma_1 = 0$. In this case, (2) becomes

$$F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{22}\sigma_3^2 + (2F_{22} - F_{44})\sigma_2\sigma_3 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_2\sigma_3 = 1. \quad (8)$$

According to the established rules in analytical geometry [14], the above equation defines an ellipse on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane if the second invariant of the above conic section

$$D = F_{22}^2 - \frac{1}{4}(2F_{22} - F_{44})^2 = \frac{1}{4}F_{44}(4F_{22} - F_{44}) = \frac{1}{4}F_{44}^2\delta > 0 \quad (9)$$

where
$$\delta = 4 - \frac{F_{44}}{F_{22}} = 4 - \frac{\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}{(\tau_{23}^*)^2}. \quad (10)$$

For conic sections, being a closed locus is equivalent to being an ellipse, as otherwise the locus would be either a parabola or a hyperbola which is deemed to be open. Condition (9) is equivalent to

$$\delta > 0. \quad (11)$$

This places a restrictive condition on some of the strength properties for the failure locus (8) to be elliptic on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane.

Unfortunately, this condition cannot be satisfied by every material. To facilitate the discussions to follow, nine different UD composites as employed in the WWFE-I, II & III [1-3] are quoted with their relevant strength properties listed in Table 1. Among the nine different materials, two of them do not satisfy condition (11). They produce negative values for δ as shown in the shaded columns and fall outside the category of (11). As a result, the failure loci for them is hyperbolic on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane, which are open.

A locus on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane is the intersection of the failure envelop in the six dimensional stress space to the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane. If the locus as an intersection is open on the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane, the failure envelope in the stress space cannot be closed. A clear conclusion obtained from the above elaboration is that an open failure envelope should be allowed for it to be applicable to all materials consistently. Imposing the restriction of closed failure envelopes for some practical materials could contradict with the necessary consequence of the other two basic assumptions of the Tsai-Wu criterion, *viz.* the failure function is quadratic and the material is transversely isotropic. The closed failure envelope assumption should therefore be abandoned as a rational step forward.

Table 1 UD composite properties and the results from the present formulation

Data from WWFE	I				II				III
Material	AS4 3501-6	T300 BSL914C	E-glass LY556	E-Glass MY750	IM7 8551-7	T300 PR-319	A-S Epoxy 1	S-2 glass Epoxy 2	G40-800 5026
σ_{1t}^* (MPa)	1950	1500	1140	1280	2560	1378	1990	1700	2750
σ_{1c}^* (MPa)	1480	900	570	800	1590	950	1500	1150	1700
σ_{2t}^* (MPa)	48	27	35	40	68 ¹	40	38	56.5 ²	70 ³
σ_{2c}^* (MPa)	200	200	114	145	185	125	150	180	210
τ_{23}^* (MPa)	55 ⁴	N/Available	50 ⁵	50 ⁶	57	45	50	40	57
δ	0.8264	N/Available	2.404	1.680	0.1280	1.531	1.720	-2.356	-0.5245
k	0.9091	N/Available	1.550	1.296	0.3578	1.237	1.311	N/Applicable	N/Applicable
r	15.76	N/Available	19.79	17.22	6.437	20.02	30.01	N/Applicable	N/Applicable
Present F_{12} ($\times 10^{-6}$) (1/MPa ²)	-2.731	N/Available	-15.23	-8.409	-0.7906	-7.647	-5.027	N/Applicable	N/Applicable
Tsai-Wu's F_{12} ($\times 10^{-6}$) (1/MPa ²)	-3.004	-5.856	-9.820	-6.488	-2.210	-6.180	-3.833	-3.546	-1.907

¹ Average taken from $\sigma_{2t}^* = 73$ and $\sigma_{3t}^* = 63$ MPa

² Average taken from $\sigma_{2t}^* = 63$ and $\sigma_{3t}^* = 50$ MPa

³ Average taken from $\sigma_{2t}^* = 75$ and $\sigma_{3t}^* = 65$ MPa

⁴ From WWFE-III [3]

⁵ From WWFE-III [3]

⁶ From WWFE-II [2]

In general terms, having an open failure envelope is not really entirely unacceptable. The failure envelope given by the von Mises criterion is open as hydrostatic stress makes no contribution to the failure and therefore the strength against this stress condition is infinite. The Tsai-Wu criterion was supposed to degenerate to that of von Mises for isotropic materials of equal tensile and compressive strengths [16], which would not be possible without allowing an open failure envelope. The openness of the failure envelope does not necessarily exclude the closeness of failure loci as the intersections between the open failure envelope and some of the representative planes in the stress space, as will be elaborated below.

4 A RATIONAL WAY OF DETERMINING F_{12}

In order to rationalise the Tsai-Wu criterion, the third assumption will be abandoned as it could contradict the other two as was shown in the previous section. Instead, it is replaced by following in order to restrict the openness as tightly as possible.

UD composites exhibit much higher strength, which can be taken as infinite for mathematical convenience, under triaxial compression at a specific stress ratio, than any of the strengths under a uniaxial stress or pure shear in principal axes.

This represents an extension from the original Tsai-Wu criterion and the outcome will be called *the rationalised Tsai-Wu criterion* to distinguish one another. A similar argument was made in the Hashin criterion [18] for biaxial compression in the plane transverse to the fibres. Its counterpart in the von Mises criterion is infinite strength under hydrostatic stress.

The coefficient F_{12} characterises the interaction between direct stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_3 ($F_{13}=F_{12}$ under the assumption of transverse isotropy) and therefore it is sufficient to consider stress states involving these direct stresses only. Given the transverse isotropy, under any stress state with $\sigma_2 \neq \sigma_3$, distortion arises in the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane which tends to undermine the strength. In order to achieve the highest strength, it is sufficient to consider only stress states having $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3$ in addition to an independent σ_1 .

Assume a triaxial compressive stress state

$$\sigma_1 = -r\sigma^* \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -\sigma^* \quad (\text{with} \quad \tau_{23} = \tau_{13} = \tau_{12} = 0) \quad (12)$$

where σ^* is a positive value indicating the level of triaxial compression when failure takes place and r the ratio between the longitudinal stress and the transverse stresses. For the stress state to be triaxial compression, one must have $r > 0$. Substituting these stresses into the failure function (1), one obtains

$$F = (r^2 F_{11} + 4F_{22} - F_{44} + 4rF_{12})(\sigma^*)^2 - (rF_1 + 2F_2)\sigma^*. \quad (13)$$

Failure is characterised by the critical condition (2)

$$f = (r^2 F_{11} + 4F_{22} - F_{44} + 4rF_{12})(\sigma^*)^2 - (rF_1 + 2F_2)\sigma^* - 1 = 0. \quad (14)$$

This defines σ^* as an implicit function of r . It is conceivable that σ^* varies with r and σ^* can take its highest value at an appropriate value of the stress ratio r . Finding the favourable stress ratio to achieve the highest strength can be presented as an extreme value problem of an implicit function which is solved mathematically below. In order to find the maximum value of σ^* , the derivative of σ^* with respect to r is required. Using the rule of derivatives of implicit functions [14], one has

$$\frac{d\sigma^*}{dr} = -\frac{\partial f}{\partial r} / \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma^*} = 0 \quad (15)$$

which leads to

$$2(rF_{11} + 2F_{12})(\sigma^*)^2 - F_1\sigma^* = 0. \quad (16)$$

This can be re-written into

$$r = -\frac{4F_{12}\sigma^* - F_1}{2F_{11}\sigma^*} = -\frac{2F_{12}}{F_{11}} + \frac{F_1}{2F_{11}\sigma^*}. \quad (17)$$

It is anticipated that, when stress ratio r satisfied the above, the material would be able to sustain a stress level significantly higher than its strengths under uniaxial stresses, i.e. σ^* can be taken to a value significantly greater than any of σ_{1t}^* , σ_{1c}^* , σ_{2t}^* , σ_{2c}^* and τ_{23}^* . If so, the term with σ^* in the denominator can be neglected and r can therefore be approximated as

$$r = -\frac{2F_{12}}{F_{11}}. \quad (18)$$

On the other hand, rearranging (14), one has

$$F_{12} = \frac{1}{4r(\sigma^*)^2} + \frac{rF_1 + 2F_2}{4r\sigma^*} - \frac{1}{4r}(r^2F_{11} + 4F_{22} - F_{44}) \quad (19)$$

where the first two terms on the right have σ^* in the denominator. With the same argument as above, these two terms can be neglected to give

$$F_{12} = -\frac{rF_{11}}{4} - \frac{1}{4r}(4F_{22} - F_{44}). \quad (20)$$

Eliminating r from (18) and (20), one obtains

$$F_{12} = \pm \frac{1}{2}k\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} \quad (21)$$

where $k = \sqrt{\delta} \geq 0$ with δ defined in (10). (22)

Dimensionless parameter δ is an important material property defined completely by the strength properties of the material. It must be non-negative for (22) to produce a real value for k . It has significant implications on the nature of the failure envelope if it becomes negative as will be explored in later in this paper.

In order to determine the sense of F_{12} as obtained in (21), substituting (21) into (18)

$$r = \mp \frac{k\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}}}{F_{11}} = \mp k\sqrt{\frac{F_{22}}{F_{11}}} \quad (23)$$

where the plus or minus signs are kept consistent with those in (21). For the stress state as defined in (12) to be triaxial compression, r must take the positive sign, i.e.

$$r = k\sqrt{\frac{F_{22}}{F_{11}}} = \sqrt{4 - \frac{\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}{(\tau_t^*)^2}} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{1t}^*\sigma_{1c}^*}{\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}}. \quad (24)$$

Accordingly, F_{12} in (21) should take the negative sign to be consistent with the sense of r , i.e.

$$F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2}k\sqrt{F_{11}F_{22}} = -\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{4 - \frac{\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}{(\tau_t^*)^2}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sigma_{1t}^*\sigma_{1c}^*\sigma_{2t}^*\sigma_{2c}^*}}. \quad (25)$$

Expression (25) can be viewed as a corrected form of the empirical expression of F_{12} in the original Tsai-Wu criterion as given in (7) with a correction factor of k . The correction is obtained here in a completely rationalised manner based on an extra assumption, i.e. UD composites exhibit much higher strengths under triaxial compression at an appropriate stress ratio than any of the strengths under a uniaxial stress or pure shear stress state in the materials' principal axes, after abandoning the closed failure envelope assumption. It is uniquely determined without any empiricism. The identical result can also be obtained alternatively by finding the principal axes of the conic section instead of the extreme value

approach as adopted above.

It can be observed that the F_{12} obtained here also enables (2) to degenerate to the failure function of the von Mises criterion for isotropic materials of equal tensile and compressive strengths, where $\sigma_{2t}^* = \sigma_{2c}^* = \sigma^*$ and $\tau_t^* = \tau_c^* = \sigma^*/\sqrt{3}$, and as a result, $\delta = 1$ and $k = 1$. In other words, (7) is not the only expression to reproduce the von Mises criterion, neither a rational one.

5 EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSIONS

For the six materials satisfying (11) as listed in Table 1, their values of δ , k and r have been calculated and listed in Table 1. The corrected values of F_{12} are comparable to the values as suggested in the original Tsai-Wu criterion but the differences are sometimes significant enough, e.g. for one of the most common types of composites, IM7 carbon/epoxy.

Using the obtained corrections for 2D in-plane stress conditions, the failure loci have been plotted in Fig. 1 for the materials shown in Table 1 where condition (11) applies and they are compared with their original form as directly obtained from the Tsai-Wu criterion. The differences the rationalism has made are marginal in most parts of these failure loci, except for E-glass/LY556 and IM7 carbon/8551-7. The most pronounced discrepancies are found in the compression - compression quadrant. This is a natural consequence of the due consideration given to the triaxial compressive strength in the present formulation. It is admirable that Tsai and Wu's empiricism hit the target with such accuracy intuitively. However, it should be pointed out that differences would be significantly more pronounced when 3D stresses are involved.

It can be observed from Table 1 that the stress ratios corresponding to the infinite strength is quite different from $r=1$, i.e. hydrostatic compression. In the light of this observation, the discussions on the infinite strength or the lack of it under hydrostatic compression would not seem relevant. Apparently, hydrostatic pressure is not the favourable stress ratio for UD composites to exhibit highest strength. Rather on the contrary, much higher longitudinal stresses than the transverse stresses should be applied in order to achieve the highest strength due to the anisotropy of the strength characteristics of UD composites.

The Hashin criterion [18] was also based on quadratic failure function. In its derivation of for matrix failure under compression, it assumed infinite strength under equal biaxial compression transverse to the fibres, which corresponded to $r=0$. The present study also challenges the validity of the assumption Hashin made there.

6 CASES WHERE $\delta < 0$

The conclusion from the previous sections is only applicable if $\delta \geq 0$. In the case of $\delta < 0$, as is the subject of this section, it is impossible to find any meaningful condition to obtain a real value for F_{12} directly. It has been demonstrated in Section 3 that the failure locus in the $\sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ plane cannot be closed in this case, neither is the envelope in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 - \sigma_3$ space. In fact, it consists of some hyperboloids, either in an hourglass configuration or as two disconnected lobes. To facilitate the elaboration in this section, the discussion can be made into two mutually exclusive but collective comprehensive scenarios, dictated purely by logic and mathematical considerations of analytical geometry on conic sections.

- (1) Allowing the failure loci in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_1 - \sigma_3$ planes to be open, i.e. $F_{12}^2 \geq F_{11}F_{22}$; or
- (2) The failure loci in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_1 - \sigma_3$ plane must be closed, i.e. $F_{12}^2 < F_{11}F_{22}$.

Fig. 1 In-plane failure loci for UD composites as indicated: comparison between the present theory and the original Tsai-Wu criterion (a) AS4 carbon/3501-6, (b) E-glass/LY556, (c) E-glass/MY750, (d) IM7 carbon/8551-7, (e) T300 carbon/PR-319 and (f) A-S carbon/epoxy 1

Given the transverse isotropy, $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ and $\sigma_1-\sigma_3$ planes are equivalent and the discussion can be made to only one of them, say, $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$. Relatively, the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ plane is by large the best known aspect of the UD composites, although data sets are still wanting under many stress ratios to offer a complete assessment. From what are available, there does not seem to be any evidence or any sensible justification remotely suggesting the likelihood of infinite strength under any stress state in the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ plane. Yet, if one chooses option (i), i.e. to allow infinite strength at a certain stress ratio, his/her first task would be to justify such a possibility which is beyond the scope of this paper. Readers are reminded that the objective of this paper is not to draw conclusion on applicability of the Tsai-Wu criterion. Rather it is to reveal all logic implications such that users could make their choice in an informed and objective manner.

If one choose to reject the possibility of any open failure locus in the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$, i.e. by choosing option (ii), then he/she will observe the following as a logic consequence of the choice under the assumptions of quadratic failure function and transverse isotropy. According to the analytical geometry, for the failure locus in the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ plane to be closed, the permissible range for F_{12} has been given in (6). Within this range, the following exercise can be carried out.

The failure loci in a special plane, $\sigma_2=\sigma_3$, is examined. Introduce the intersection of this plane with the $\sigma_1=0$ plane as a new axis $\sigma_t = \sigma_2/\sqrt{2} = \sigma_3/\sqrt{2}$ so that it is in the same scale as σ_2 and σ_3 . The $\sigma_2=\sigma_3$ plane can also be called the $\sigma_t-\sigma_1$ plane. If one plots the failure loci in the $\sigma_t-\sigma_1$ plane for all values of F_{12} permissible according to (6), some envelopes can be obtained, as shown in Figs 2(a) and (b) for S-2 glass/Epoxy 2 and G40-800/5026, respectively, as two materials in Table 1 falling into the current category. The shaded areas correspond to condition $F<1$, defining the safe zone of the stress states for the material, although the disconnected shaded part on the right in Fig. 2(b) is not accessible as loading process must start from the origin and any accessible state should be connected to the origin. Despite the disparity in appearance between Figs. 2(a) and (b), some common observations can be made: (a) There are infinite number of stress ratios between σ_1 and σ_t , at which infinite strengths can be obtained and (b) Some of such stress ratios involve tensile stress in the fibre direction.

As a conservative measure of the safe zone, one can take the darkly shaded subzone defined by the dashed lines which are parallel to the asymptotes to the envelope boundaries next them.

To summarise the discussion on the case of $\delta<0$, it is clear that any choice of the value of F_{12} will lead to scenarios of infinite strength under stress states other than triaxial compression, which are hard to defend. This has been implied in any prediction of the Tsai-Wu criterion employing whatever value of F_{12} , no matter how good the agreement is in comparison with experimental data in one aspect or another. If the value of F_{12} is so chosen that $F_{12}^2 \geq F_{11}F_{22}$, the failure loci in the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ and $\sigma_1-\sigma_3$ planes will be open, either as a parabola or hyperbola. Alternatively, if $F_{12}^2 < F_{11}F_{22}$, while it is possible to keep the failure locus closed in the $\sigma_1-\sigma_2$ plane as shown in Fig.1, infinite strengths are inevitable under triaxial stresses at infinite number of stress ratios, where the stress along fibres is tensile while the transverse stresses are compressive, as shown in Fig. 2. The dilemma is a logic consequence of the use of a single quadratic failure function and the transverse isotropy of the material as the two basic assumptions in the Tsai-Wu criterion. The position cannot be altered unless one or both basic assumptions are abandoned.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 The envelope of failure loci in the $\sigma_t - \sigma_1$ plane for all permissible values of F_{12} if the failure loci in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_1 - \sigma_3$ planes remain closed (a) S-2 glass/Epoxy 2 and (b) G40-800/5026

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the quadratic failure function as proposed by Tsai and Wu [4] has been subjected to a systematic examination from the mathematical perspective guided by the principles of analytical geometry. It has been first argued that the failure envelope in the stress space cannot be kept closed for all materials and it is therefore more appropriate to manage the opening than prohibiting it. A non-dimensional parameter $\delta = 4 - \sigma_{2t}^* \sigma_{2c}^* / (\tau_{23}^*)^2$ has been introduced which is completely determined by material's conventional strength properties. The sense of this parameter divides all UD composites into two categories, i.e. $\delta \geq 0$ and $\delta < 0$. For the former category, allowing infinite strength under a certain triaxial compressive stress ratio provides a condition for the unique determination of the interactive coefficient F_{12} . This helps to eliminate the empiricism associated with this coefficient ever since the birth of the Tsai-Wu criterion. The obtained rational expression of F_{12} can be considered as a corrected form from that in the original Tsai-Wu criterion. It has also been shown that such rationalised Tsai-Wu criterion is also capable of reproducing the von Mises criterion for isotropic materials of equal tensile and compressive strengths.

For the category of $\delta < 0$, if one chose to apply the Tsai-Wu criterion, it has been rigorously established in this paper that any value of F_{12} would imply features hard to defend, either to allow the failure locus in the $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ to be open, i.e. allowing infinite strength under an in-plane stress state, or to allow a range of triaxial stress states to exhibit infinite strength, including some involving tension in the fibre direction.

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